

Modern Masonry Shear-wall Database (MoMaS-DB 2026)

This Zenodo record has been created to support the manuscript:

Mukattash, N., Butenweg, C., Kubalski, T., and Klinkel, S. (2026). *A novel approach for the estimation of seismic drift capacity in unreinforced masonry (URM) shear walls based on governing structural parameters.*

MoMaS-DB is a comprehensive database of experimental in-plane cyclic tests on unreinforced masonry (URM) shear walls. The database includes information on masonry materials, wall geometries, loading conditions, failure modes, load–displacement curves, and drift capacities.

The complete database is currently undergoing final review and quality control. The full dataset and associated files will be uploaded in a subsequent version of this Zenodo record prior to final acceptance of the associated journal article. Future releases may also incorporate additional experimental results and updates.

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